

PULSE: Real-Time Monitoring and Analysis Framework Leveraging Twitter Data

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Abstract—As social media platforms continue to shape modern communication, understanding and harnessing the wealth of information they offer has become increasingly crucial. The nature of the data that these platforms provide makes them the emerging resource for data collection to conduct research ranging from measuring sentiments of the people over a particular trend in society to drafting a major policy by governing agencies. This paper presents PULSE, a powerful tool developed by Decision Theater™ (DT) at Arizona State University in the United States, designed to extract valuable insights from Twitter. PULSE provides researchers and organizations with access to a curated dataset of public opinions and discussions across diverse research areas. Further, the tool uses various machine learning and data analytical algorithms to derive valuable insights on the subject under research. These insights are efficiently displayed using an interactive dashboard to assist the researchers in extracting useful insights to draw appropriate conclusions. The paper also illustrates the technical functionalities and visualization capabilities of the tool with the case study on Hurricane Laura.

Keywords— *Twitter data, social media analytics, real-time data processing, sentiment analysis, trend detection, data visualization.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The opinions and needs of the public contribute to the establishment of decision-making centers. Decision makers need to gather information to bring productive outcomes that ease the lives of the public. Traditionally, surveys have been conducted for collecting and measuring public opinion for a long time. However, the reduction in response rates for the surveys have raised a concern over the sustainability of the survey research and its legitimacy to randomize samples of individuals to represent an entire population [1]. Further, some research requires datasets that extend over time, while other critical research requires real-time data that allows gauging current community sentiment around a topic. These data from surveys typically don't have value after some time. The framework used to collect data is not reusable. So, these problems can be overcome by using dynamic data (real-time) data that addresses these issues.

The proliferation of modern technologies has led policymakers and researchers to recognize the need to delve into emerging data sources like social media for various decision-making processes [2]. Various social networks have been utilized as a mode of communication and socialization,

supporting a social structure as a communication medium between individuals and organizations over the internet [3].

Social media provides large amounts of rapidly refreshing, rich, and diverse data that differs by spatial, demographic, and socio-economic factors. By applying machine learning algorithms and advanced analytics, researchers can identify significant patterns and gain insights into the perceptions, sentiments, and behaviors of communities. This enables the researchers to understand how specific groups with shared characteristics are influenced by, and in turn, influence other groups in the online space [2].

As a giant in social media, Twitter offers an open environment where people all around the world can share information and opinions, emerging as a real-time repository of human thoughts that can be exploited by researchers and applications [3]. Twitter receives a large volume of publicly available data which provides more insights about the public opinion than what a survey instrument could capture [4]. As Twitter supports researchers by providing Application Programming Interfaces (API's) and has a significantly greater number of active user communities, it is more convenient to collect enormous public opinions and further capture insights. Additionally, by providing users with a broader background including but not limited to common individuals, celebrities, politicians, domain experts, etc. [5], Twitter data helps the randomization of population to collect the data.

In this paper, we present the tool, PULSE, which was developed by Decision Theater™ (DT) at Arizona State University. The tool was created to empower researchers and organizations by utilizing Twitter data analytics. It allows them to easily access insights into community needs and understand public opinions on various topics. This knowledge enables them to make informed decisions and take more effective actions than ever before.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Twitter, a microblogging application, has gained tremendous popularity over the last decade as a social platform to share information across all domains. This has helped researchers and policymakers of different backgrounds to extract data required for their research or decision making respectively. It is highly notable that, irrespective of the domain of the research, Twitter provides an ample amount of data required for research in fields such as politics [6], travel [7], health [8] [9], education [10], climate change [11], etc.

Further, public governing organizations can obtain the necessary information to make decisions on various aspects that fulfill the requirements of the community. Some examples include policy modeling, infrastructure development, and natural hazard measures [12][13].

Twitter has recognized itself as a great resource for data collection in research activities [14]. The article [14], discusses the usage of various tools in Twitter data collection and analysis, while also exploring the skillsets essential to conduct research on Twitter data. A combination of both manual and automated approaches has been utilized to analyze data obtained from Twitter [14]. However, the cost associated with some of the tools for data collection and analysis might prove to be significantly overbearing [14]. Several aspects need to be carefully considered such as research questions, strategies for sample size, and ethical considerations when working with data from social media [14].

A python-based framework has been developed for conducting network analysis in [15], where Twitter data is extracted based on a keyword query (hashtag, URL, names, etc.) using a Python wrapper for the Twitter API, Tweepy. Further, this data is cleaned and used for constructing a network of all the users. To analyze this network, various network analysis algorithms are used such as degree distribution, betweenness and closeness centrality measures, community detection, and average clustering. The tool developed by the author assists the researchers to analyze the Twitter data on a very granular level and to understand the propagation of hashtags. The work also monitors the location of the Twitter users by using GeoPy and updates the mapping of location of the users.

TwitterNews+, a low computational cost solution to detect events from a high-volume streaming-data source in real-time, has been proposed in [16]. TwitterNews+ achieves this through incorporating specialized inverted indices and an incremental clustering approach that detects both major and minor newsworthy events in real-time. The Search Module handles the first stage of the system and facilitates a fast retrieval of similar tweets to provide a binary decision on the novelty of an input tweet. The EventCluster Module handles the second stage of the system and assigns each tweet to an event cluster through its processing. Further, authors have determined optimal parameter settings through their analysis using one-at-a-time sensitivity measures.

The literature review suggests that Twitter data analytics has become an essential part of analyzing public opinion required for research and policymaking. However, the overall process of data collection and cleaning to analysis and interpretation is highly technology-intensive and can be expensive. Hence, it is crucial to develop a cost-effective and comprehensive tool that enables the researchers to obtain the desired outcomes with ease. In this regard, PULSE, a single-stop solution for Twitter data analytics, is discussed in the subsequent sections.

III. PULSE FRAMEWORK

With the vision of developing models that not only provide insights into communities' current demands and behaviors, but also to help understand people's attitudes and expectations toward a change — or a proposed change — in various domains of interests, DT has developed a tool called PULSE. The tool assists to exponentially expand the access of researchers and other organizations to an up to date, filtered

dataset of public opinion and discussions around virtually any research area. The primary objectives of the tool include:

- To increase visibility of the outcomes through a public-facing dashboard that provides real-time access to users' reactions or opinions about specific policies or topics.
- To give researchers the ability to mine large amounts of data on different topics through filtering by keywords, location, user accounts, geographical attributes, and language of search. Researchers will be able to access topic-specific data and analyze it through an interactive dashboard.
- To provide researchers with crowd-sourced, location-specific enriched data on residents' attitudes, values, perceptions, and preferences around options or changes, which can be employed in current and future research.

A. Workflow

First, users identify and define the key terms, search parameters, and research objectives. Then DT creates a project in PULSE based on the requirements provided by the researchers and stakeholders. Next, we determine the mechanisms for analysis and implement the appropriate algorithms, if needed, to gather and analyze information in the PULSE framework, as shown in Figure 1. These techniques uncover granular insights while filtering out the irrelevant data. Information is then presented on a custom-developed graphic dashboard and DT researchers work with users to identify appropriate visualization techniques to communicate new insights.

Figure 1: PULSE Framework

B. Implementation

1) *Data collection and processing:* The tool uses distributed systems to collect live real-time data from Twitter via Twitter streaming API. It focuses on collecting tweets that match specific keywords determined by the user. The data is further processed to extract the relevant and important attributes such as language, hashtags, mentions, location, URL's, etc. After the attribute extraction step, the tweets are subject to machine learning and data analysis algorithms. These algorithms analyze the attributes within the tweets to derive insights and valuable information to be showcased to the end users.

a) *Extraction of sentiment:* Sentiment analysis is at the heart of PULSE. A real-time sentiment analysis model that includes training the sentiment algorithm on existing tweets is followed by validation and testing. The model is built using the open source models DeepMoji [17] and Unsupervised Sentiment Neuron [18]. The DeepMoji model is used to

predict emojis; this model is trained from 1.2 billion tweets that are filtered from 55 billion tweets. The tool extends the model to extract sentiment and emotion and to detect sarcasm.

b) *Network analysis*: Analyzing data from all users is not necessary to find prominent conversational issues and extract meaningful sentiment [19]. So the tool has been developed to use network analysis to understand influential Twitter users' statements, predictions, opinions, and impact. Picking the highly active users gives information about the most-talked-about issues in the Twittersphere, thus helping researchers to access voices related to the topic of interest. First, the tool makes use of specific metrics to capture prominent users. Then, it analyzes the sentiment of tweets and the sentiment of the reactions to the influential tweets from prominent users and depicts the results in a multidimensional data representation [20].

2) *Data indexing and storage*: The generated insights, along with the original tweet data, are then stored for future reference and analysis. This data is also used for querying and displaying results on the dashboard. A distributed database is used to store the indexed data and results. Usage of a distributed database provides high-speed query, search, and aggregation capabilities by serving parts of queries from the nodes in the distributed system along with providing redundancy in case of downtime [21].

3) *Visualization dashboard*: The tool offers a user-interface for project creation, project selection, project configuration, and controls. The results from the data collection and analysis are queried and made accessible through a real-time dashboard for the users. This dashboard presents various data analytics, including sentiment analysis, network analysis, visualizations, and charts. Using these visualization dashboards, researchers can gain valuable insights from the analyzed data. The interactive nature of the dashboards allows for a comprehensive exploration of the findings, empowering researchers to extract meaningful information and draw conclusions based on the presented visual representations.

C. Dashboard

A user-friendly dashboard has been developed as the front-facing component of the tool for researchers and stakeholders. This dashboard enables users to set filtering parameters and visualize various analytical outputs as graphs. Figure 2 provides a preview of the dashboard.

Components of the dashboard:

1) *Filters tab*: The tab highlights the filters selected. Filters can be easily added or removed as needed. Filters can be added by clicking on any of the bar or pie graph segments, time series graph and search box.

2) *Tweet feed*: This section displays a small subset of tweets that have been collected based on the provided keywords. Users are provided an option to view a specific type of tweets and current options include tweets with links, tweets containing photos or tweets containing videos.

3) *Time series*: The Time Series graph helps visualize data points at successive time intervals and helps identify the trends which can lead to further analysis. Any particular time frame ranging from hours to weeks or months can be chosen using the zoom feature. Once a particular time frame is chosen, all the visualizations of the dashboard will be updated accordingly. An instance of time based filtering is shown in Figure 3, where tweets between the specified range are filtered for further analysis.

Figure 2. Layout of the dashboard

Figure 3. Filtering based on time.

4) *Barcharts*: Vertical bar charts are used to represent the categorical data, where the height of the bar on the Y-axis corresponds to the quantity of each data point on the X-axis. The bar charts are generated for six attributes from the data. Each bar chart gives the count of each parameter in the entire Twitter dataset within a particular time frame. The bar charts are dynamic and adjust accordingly when filters are applied. Clicking on individual bars allows users to filter the data based on the selected data point. Upon selecting a specific value, the entire dashboard updates its results accordingly.

The click functionality of the tool enables users to gain more insights on a particular bar by selecting it.

Attributes represented by bar charts:

a) *Hashtags*: Twitter hashtags, represented by the '#' symbol, connect users to tweets with the same hashtag and help in categorizing keywords or identifying topics of interest. The bar chart shows frequently used hashtags based on the filters that are extracted from Twitter data. Users can study this chart to recognize popular hashtags and enhance their filters.

b) *Mentions*: Mentions refer to tweets that include another person's username anywhere in the tweet.

c) *Users*: Shows the users who tweeted the most along with their tweet count.

d) *User Interface*: Users use various interfaces to access Twitter. This bar chart shows which interfaces are used the most to tweet and which ones are used rarely.

e) *User Language*: Tweets that match the keywords are collected in all languages, this chart highlights the most used languages.

f) *Hostname of URL*: Lists the variety of hostnames mentioned in the tweets.

5) *Pie Charts*: The tool represents three attributes in the data as pie charts. Each distribution in the pie chart can be selected as a filter which updates the entire dashboard. The pie charts will update based on the filtering criteria.

a) *Type of Tweet*: In general, tweets are grouped into original tweet, re-tweet, reply to tweet and a quote (a quote is a retweet that allows a user to add their own comments to the tweet). This pie chart represents the distribution of tweets collected.

b) *Tweet Summary*: This chart gives information on what percentage of the tweets are taking on into consideration based on the filters applied on the dashboard.

c) *Sentiments*: Sentiment Analysis results of the dataset are displayed in this pie chart. Positive, negative, and neutral sentiments display the percentage of tweets that belong to each of those categories. Unclassified tweets will be counted under the Confused category.

6) *Network Map*: The network diagram allows users to quickly understand relationships in the data. Nodes and edges make up the network map. It exposes trends and aids in anomaly detection. The Network Map is updated based on the filtering criteria.

7) *World Map*: Shows the location distribution of geo-coded tweets.

8) *Word Cloud*: This visualization shows the most frequently used words in tweets. The word size is larger for words that appear more frequently in the data and the size is smaller for words that appear less frequently. The Word Cloud is updated based on the filtering criteria.

The key advantage of this tool lies in its modular design. It offers flexibility for researchers to incorporate additional functions, modules, or visualizations as required. This allows for seamless integration of analytics modules and graph representations tailored to a specific research domain. Furthermore, the tool operates as a web-based application,

eliminating the necessity for software support and reducing dependence on technological assistance.

IV. CASE STUDY

Hurricane Laura was a Category 4 hurricane that caused significant destruction and loss of life. It shares the record with the 1856 Last Island hurricane and 2021's Hurricane Ida as the strongest hurricanes to make landfall in Louisiana, based on maximum sustained winds [22]. The case study of Hurricane Laura has been conducted to study the reaction over Twitter using the PULSE tool. Nearly 1.8M tweets were captured during a short period of 26th August to 1st September 2020. As shown in Figure 4, the time series graph shows the tweets captured over the period and it is observed that the number of tweets were at its peak during the intense period of the Hurricane Laura between 26th to 29th of August 2020 [22].

Figure 4. Time series graph between specified dates

These bar charts represent attribute level information and will assist in further analysis of the tweets. For example, one may click on the hashtag "trump2020" on the Figure 6, and the selection applies to the rest of the charts in the dashboard. Using this feature, researchers can perform analysis on how people are responding to this natural disaster and express their expectations/concerns with the President of the United States of America at the time.

Figure 5. Overview of bar charts in the dashboard

The "Type of Tweets" pie chart represents another significant aspect. It provides insights into the interactions among Twitter users and highlights the influence certain groups of individuals have over larger communities. Figure 7 illustrates

that approximately 80% of the tweets captured were retweets, which highlights the substantial impact a select few can have on the broader Twitter user base. Furthermore, the sentiments of the people can be classified based on the tweet and be divided into positive, negative, or neutral, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6. Bar chart for hashtags dashboard

Figure 7. Pie Chart representing Type of tweets.

The tool also provides a network map (Figure 9) assisting in gauging the trends in the relationship between the people in the network and how the behavior of the system is influenced by these relationships. The circle represents the people, and the edges between them represent the connections. The bigger the nodes are, the larger influence that user has. Furthermore, the World Map (Figure 10), assists to analyze the location-based insights as it provides details on location distribution of geo-coded tweets. The information on World Map also represents the response across the globe and assists in location-based analysis. The word cloud component of the dashboard helps to visualize the most used keywords among

the tweets and size corresponds to the frequency of usage of the keyword (Figure 11).

V. CONCLUSION

As the influence of social media and other interaction platforms continues to grow, users are increasingly recognizing their impact. Twitter, in particular, has seen a surge in its user base, leading to the displacement of traditional mass communication channels such as newspapers, television, and radio. Leveraging the insights collected from these platforms to make informed decisions for the betterment of future generations is a gamechanger. The PULSE tool represents such an initiative and has showcased remarkable potential in effectively collecting, processing, and analyzing data from Twitter in real time. By presenting the analyzed results through an intuitive and user-friendly dashboard, it offers an unbiased perspective to an audience that may otherwise be subject to inherent bias. This empowers researchers, stakeholders, and the general public to make well-informed decisions based on accurate and comprehensive information. Ultimately, the PULSE tool harnesses the invaluable information available on social media platforms like Twitter for the greater benefit of society as a whole.

In this iteration of PULSE, the emphasis was placed on data collection specifically from Twitter. However, in the subsequent phase of the project, the goal is to transform PULSE into a versatile platform capable of gathering available data from various social media platforms, such as Instagram, Facebook, Reddit, and more. Additionally, there is a plan to incorporate modules that can extract data from flat files, including CSV, Excel, and TXT formats. To enhance the platform's functionality, efforts will be made to facilitate the integration of new data analysis and machine learning models into the existing framework. This will provide researchers with the flexibility to incorporate cutting-edge techniques and algorithms into their analyses. As part of this development, an automated pipeline will be established, allowing users to dynamically select and apply different models on the fly. This pipeline will streamline the process of collecting data from different sources and processing it through the chosen models, enabling efficient and comprehensive analysis across diverse datasets.

Figure 8. Pie Chart representing the emotions of the people.

Figure 9. Network analysis of the tool

Figure 10. World map highlighting the locations the tweets.

Figure 11. Word Cloud representing keywords.

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